

1 **A Public Website of Rock Mechanics Database from Earth Mechanics**
2 **Institute (EMI) at Colorado School of Mines (CSM)**

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11 strength (UCS), Brazilian tensile strength (BTS), Cerchar abrasivity index (CAI), and Punch
12 penetration (PP) test.

13
14 **1. INTRODUCTION**

15 Mechanical properties of rocks are a pivotal factor in geostructure construction, mining,
16 and rock engineering application because rock mechanical properties significantly influence
17 downstream engineering processes such as blasting, excavating and rock failures (Ghassemi 2012;
18 Goetze and Evans 1979; Jing 2003; Perras and Diederichs 2014). Since rock mechanical properties
19 vary with many other factors (e.g. density, porosity, permeability, mineral composition,
20 inhomogeneities, moisture content, temperature, etc.) (Kim et al. 2009; Kim et al. 2010; Kim et al.
21 2012a; Kim et al. 2012b; Schumacher and Kim 2013; Schumacher and Kim 2014; Sieter et al.
22 2015), a comprehensive view of rock mechanics is required. In order to eliminate this deficit in
23 knowledge, the Earth Mechanics Institute was founded at the Colorado School of Mines to assist
24 in sharing the benefits of new excavation technologies with the field of underground civil and
25 mining construction. For more than 40 years, the EMI has worked to advance the science of
26 physical property tests and measurements, and has also developed an industry-leading collection
27 of mechanical rock excavation tools. The data and models generated by the institute have impacted
28 construction projects worldwide.

29 However, to improve data accessibility to the public, including students, researchers,
30 colleagues, and industry workers, the vast collection of data generated by the EMI naturally solicits

31 the need for analytical and visualization tools. In addition, the vast collection of data requires a
32 strong organizational scheme. The implementation described in this paper serves as an example of
33 such a solution. It leverages a relational database to organize data into a well-structured schema
34 and a server-side web programming language to serve dynamic content from the database to the
35 client for visualization and analysis.

36 The motivation behind a comprehensive EMI rock mechanics database stems from the
37 perpetual need for highly specific rock mechanics data on demand. Virtually all construction or
38 mining projects require significant rock mechanics research in the exploration stage of the project
39 before the design process can begin. This research often requires the retrieval of a very specific
40 characteristic of a specific rock or soil type, which may be difficult without an organized collection
41 of such information.

42 The purpose of this database is to extensively fingerprint a collection of rocks such that
43 any desired characteristic of a given rock can be easily obtained with a high level of confidence in
44 the accuracy of the data. In addition to the retrieval of information, the database also aims to
45 facilitate the discovery of trends and patterns amidst a large collection of data. Just as the biology
46 “Genbank[®]” database (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) seeks to amass large quantities of data and
47 explain the significance and importance of certain patterns (Benson et al. 2013), likewise a “rock
48 bank” database seeks to provide insight into the existence and causation of patterns in rock
49 mechanics.

50 The development of a rock mechanics database is also driven by the need to organize and
51 display an otherwise unmanageable quantity of data. This implementation includes over 26,000
52 data samples furnished by the EMI, which is impractical to manage with simple spreadsheet tools
53 but trivial with a relational database. A relational database also immensely improves the flexibility
54 and power provided to the user (Peters et al. 2014). Leveraging a database allows a developer to
55 build powerful, customized tools to display and analyze data. Also, such tools are not limited to a
56 certain department or university, but can be accessed publicly over the web by scientists, engineers,
57 and students throughout the world.

58

59 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

60 ***2.1 EMI rock mechanics database***

61 The plot tool of the EMI rock mechanics database
62 (<http://emirockmechanicsdatabase.mines.edu>) was designed to facilitate the retrieval, analysis, and
63 inference of specific rock mechanics data. The database supporting this tool contains more than
64 26,000 entries of test data collected from a variety of EMI-based rock mechanics tests. These tests
65 include unconfined compressive strength (UCS), Brazilian tensile strength (BTS), Cerchar
66 abrasivity index (CAI), punch penetration, cohesion, direction shear, triaxial confining, and
67 density. This tool was constructed to allow the user to plot the results from two of these rock
68 mechanics tests against each other for a given rock characteristic, and from there build a statistical
69 model describing the relationship.

70

71 ***2.2 Construction of the EMI rock mechanics database***

72 The initial step in building an EMI rock mechanics database is the schema design (Fig. 1).
73 A well-designed schema minimizes any kind of data duplication while still maintaining a structure
74 that is straightforward to query. For a sufficiently large collection of geomechanics data, it
75 naturally follows that data should be separated into several relations (or tables) such as sample
76 location and test metadata, as well as individual tables for each type of test.

77 MySQL Server (v5.7) with an InnoDB Engine was used to build the tables, since MySQL
78 is free and simple to setup, and its relational database model is ideal for this application. Although
79 NoSQL databases, such as MongoDB, or distributed databases, such as Hadoop, are becoming
80 increasingly popular, MySQL is still a better choice because of the flexibility provided by a
81 relational model and the power provided by SQL (Structured Query Language).

82 A simplified diagram of the implemented schema is shown in Figure 1. As mentioned
83 earlier, the schema features a distributed relational design that separates metadata and location data
84 from each of the eight tables of test data: Brazilian tensile strength (BTS), Cerchar abrasivity index
85 (CAI), cohesion, density, direct shear, punch penetration, triaxial compression test, and unconfined
86 compressive strength (UCS) (Fig. 2). The primary key of each test data table, ID, is a foreign key
87 to the ID column of the main 'EMI data' table (Fig. 2). Furthermore, a location key in the 'EMI
88 data' table is a foreign key to the ID column in the Location table. Additional tables could be used
89 to keep track of other data, if the need arises. The design was modular so that such modifications
90 could be made.

91 Data import techniques vary drastically depending on implementation. Some of the most

92 popular practices are building a custom file-parsing script or exporting an existing Microsoft
93 Access database as a MySQL database. More advanced users are encouraged to pursue a
94 customized approach, but by far the simplest approach is using Microsoft Access. Within Access
95 it is trivial to import data from Excel or CSV files, organize that data into tables, and then export
96 the data to a new MySQL database.

97 After data has been entered into the database, the next logical step is to design an interface
98 in which that data may be displayed and analyzed. Although many interface platforms are
99 available, a web-based interface is often simplest to build and maintain. A server side web
100 programming language, such as PHP (PHP: Hypertext Processor) or JSP (Java Server Pages),
101 should also be chosen to generate dynamic content for the interface. We chose PHP as the server-
102 side language and JavaScript with HTML (Hyper Text Markup Language)/CSS (Cascading Style
103 Sheets) as the client-side languages. As the user interacts with the web interface, Asynchronous
104 Javascript and XML (or AJAX) requests are sent to the server in the form of HTTP GET requests.
105 The server responds to these HTTP GET requests for specific data and returns a JSON (JavaScript
106 Object Notation) object containing the requested data. JavaScript running on the client then parses
107 the object, calculates various statistics, including means, standard deviations, and a trend line (and
108 the corresponding standard error), and then plots the data on a graph, using a jQuery-based library
109 for JavaScript. This specific implementation allows the user to simultaneously plot data from two
110 different tests for a given characteristic of rock, generate a custom regression model, and view the
111 statistics compiled for the selected subset of data. Figure 3 depicts a simple HTML form used to
112 generate plots, while Figure 4 illustrates a sample plot, trend line, and sample statistics.

113

114 ***2.3 User instruction and guide***

115 In order to use the plot tool of the EMI rock mechanics database, select up to two distinct
116 rocks using the ‘Rock Type’ and ‘Characteristic’ selectors in the table above. Then, choose two
117 independent properties to plot against each other using the ‘Property #1’ and ‘Property #2’
118 selectors. The final column may be used to filter the final results by the type of failure experienced
119 during the test (structural/non-structural) and by the bedding type of the sample
120 (parallel/perpendicular). More detailed usage instruction with snapshot images is provided at the
121 EMI rock mechanics website (<http://emirockmechanicsdatabase.mines.edu/emigraphs.php>).

122

123 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

124 The EMI rock mechanics database (<http://emirockmechanicsdatabase.mines.edu>) was
125 constructed to open rock mechanics data to the public for use by students, researchers, and industry
126 workers. As the EMI database contains a vast collection of data including statistical analyses and
127 visualization tools, we explain the EMI database in detail for the convenience of users.

128

129 **3.1 EMI rock mechanics database**

130 Figure 3 shows a request for data. There are four separate columns in the form that are
131 described in the following sections. The two leftmost columns in this form are used to select one
132 (or two) specific rock types(s) from the database. The first column is used to select the first rock
133 type and is mandatory (Fig. 3A), whereas the second column is used to select the second rock type
134 and is optional (Fig. 3B). In other words, no less than one and no more than two distinct rock types
135 may be selected at one time. Figure 3A shows an example query with sedimentary sandstone
136 selected as the first rock type and characteristic, respectively. The second rock type was unselected
137 in this example (Fig. 3B), but another rock type could be selected as shown in Figure 5. At the
138 time of writing, up to 142 sedimentary rocks, 106 metamorphic rocks, and 25 igneous rocks
139 comprising over 26,000 data points may be queried using the first and second columns (Fig 3A
140 and 3B).

141 The third column handles rock mechanical and physical properties (Fig. 3C). Two distinct
142 properties should be chosen in this step so that an XY plot can be generated of the selected data in
143 a following step. Eight different properties of the rocks can be selected: (1) UCS, (2) BTS, (3)
144 CAI, (4) direct shear, (5) cohesion, (6) triaxial confining, (7) punch penetration, and (8) density.
145 Figure 3C shows a continuation of the sandstone example, choosing density and unconfined
146 compressive strength as the selected properties. In practice, some property pairs show significant
147 statistical correlations, while some may return insignificant correlations or empty results.

148 Finally, the fourth column allows for further filtering of the data returned from the database
149 (Fig. 3D). The first row allows for filtering based on the type of failure experienced during the test
150 (structural/non-structural/all). The second row allows for filtering based on the bedding direction
151 of the samples (parallel/perpendicular/all bedding). Figure 3D shows a continuation of the
152 sandstone example with the results filtered by non-structural failure with all bedding directions.
153 Once the form has been filled out, click the “submit” button to submit the request and view the

154 results.

155 If results have been found for the requested parameters, a graph and statistical model will
156 be displayed on the screen (Fig 4a). Data points are color coded in the key (in the bottom right
157 corner) to differentiate results from each rock type in the result set. In the table below the graph
158 labeled “Regression Data”, the first column contains a dropdown box which may be used to
159 customize the statistical model. The following regression types are supported: linear, exponential,
160 logarithmic, power, square, and cubic. In the subsequent columns, the model parameters
161 (coefficients), R^2 value, p-value, and sample count are shown (Fig. 4B). In the regression data table
162 shown in Figure 4B, the R^2 value reveals how well a database plot is correlated between the
163 sandstone density and UCS. However, the R^2 is not a determinant to judge statistical significance
164 of the correlation between the density and UCS. Instead, the regression model should be
165 determined by p-value (< 0.05). The R^2 value for the correlation between the density and UCS is
166 ~ 0.55 , and p-value is quite small ($p < 0.05$) (Fig. 4B). As a result, the correlation between the
167 density and UCS is statistically significant as the p-value is less than 0.05, supporting that the
168 density has a meaningful relationship to the UCS, and the regression model is adequate. Thus, the
169 result obtained from the database plot suggest that the sandstone density positively correlates with
170 UCS. Finally, the last two tables on the page show statistics about the results returned from each
171 test that corresponds to the search parameters (Fig. 4C).

172 More noticeably, two different rock types can be analyzed simultaneously with the same
173 database plot (Fig. 5). Figure 5 shows a database plot of metamorphic gneiss and igneous granite
174 with the correlation between BTS and UCS. Five gneiss and eight granite data are displayed with
175 yellow and orange colors on the database plot, respectively. According to the regression data table,
176 the R^2 value is ~ 0.46 and the p-value is less than 0.05, supporting the conclusion that mechanical
177 correlation between BTS and UCS is significant.

178 It is clear that the EMI database can provide students, researchers, colleagues, and industry
179 workers with preliminary and insightful information related to rock mechanics and geotechnics,
180 assisting in their project design, analysis, and data interpretation.

181

182 ***3.2 Comparison to other databases***

183 Some online geoscience databases such as the Geochemical Rock Database-Query
184 (<http://georoc.mpch-mainz.gwdg.de/georoc>), Geochemical Earth Reference Model

185 (<https://earthref.org/GERM>), World Stress Map (<http://dc-app3-14.gfz->
186 potsdam.de/pub/stress_data/stress_data_frame.html), Allied Geophysics Laboratory Data Portal
187 (<http://www.agl.uh.edu/resources-data.php>), and Canada-Geoscience Data
188 (<http://gdr.agg.nrcan.gc.ca/gdrdap/dap/search-eng.php>) have been developed in response to rapid
189 geo-technological progress. Massive datasets are publicly available for inspection and analysis.
190 However, to our knowledge there does not exist a rock mechanics database which provides
191 massive rock mechanics data (more than 20,000 entries) tested only in the EMI laboratory and
192 includes statistical analyses. In contrast to most geoscience databases constructed based on
193 comprehensive collection of published analyses, all data provided at the EMI website has been
194 collected in a single laboratory (EMI), so that experimental variations generated by operators and
195 machines could be minimized. Consequently, the reliability of the data in the EMI database is very
196 high.

197 In addition, the EMI database is very powerful due to its application-specific
198 customizability. The main focus of this specific implementation is on a flexible user interface
199 coupled with an emphasis on statistical analysis of a broad set of data. The data filtering
200 mechanism is simple to operate and allows for open-ended analysis. Instead of separating the data
201 into numerous subgroups or smaller repositories, this implementation unifies all samples in the
202 database into a single pool which can be filtered and analyzed together. Thus, two otherwise very
203 different samples may be compared side by side, which is quite difficult in other implementations.

204 Statistical analysis is also a significant focus of this implementation. The regression tool
205 allows for the generation of a custom regression model for any combination of rock characteristics,
206 test types, and x-y relationships (linear, exponential, power, logarithmic, square, cubic, etc.). This
207 flexibility is very useful when it comes to correlation analysis of a wide collection of rock
208 characteristics and rock mechanics data. Thus, the goal of such an implementation is not to
209 compete in scale with other online geoscience databases, but rather to show the feasibility of the
210 development of a customized database that meets application-specific requirements.

211

212 ***3.3 Perspective***

213 The concept of the EMI rock mechanics database is also extensible to a somewhat larger
214 literature-sourced database. Recent studies have even shown the feasibility of automating this
215 process (Liolios and Exadaktylos 2011). Although primary sources of data are preferable,

216 secondary sources are very helpful in incorporating data that would otherwise be prohibitive to
217 obtain. Collecting and incorporating published data sets into the database can improve the
218 completeness of the database, especially for dynamic rock mechanical properties as the EMI
219 database does not include the dynamic mechanical properties. Because mechanical properties
220 differ significantly in static and dynamic conditions (Kim and Changani 2016), including the
221 dynamic mechanical properties will enhance the database value. In addition, as rock mechanical
222 properties vary with environment factors such as water and temperature, updating some published
223 data regarding water content and temperature effects on rock mechanical properties would be
224 useful to improve the database quality.

225 The development of an EMI rock mechanics database is a slow process due to the quantity
226 and uniformity of data required to make such a tool effective. This database is still in its early
227 stages, although it certainly does return useful information. This deficit will be resolved as more
228 data is collected, verified and added to the database. We believe that the EMI database will be
229 useful to the public in providing knowledge of rock mechanics as well as assisting in the design
230 and interpretation phases of a variety of projects related to mining, geotechnical applications, and
231 geostructure construction.

232

233 ***3.4 Rock mechanics data upload by peer researchers***

234 Although the single-laboratory approach to rock mechanics databases is beneficial for
235 eliminating errors and discrepancies among the data caused by experimental variations, a more
236 complete and extensive dataset can be constructed with academic collaboration. For this reason,
237 the EMI database tool has been extended to allow peer researchers to contribute their data to the
238 rock mechanics database (Figure 6).

239 In order to ensure quality and maintain accuracy of the dataset, peer contributions will
240 undergo a verification process. Only contributions that are sourced from a work that has been
241 published in peer-reviewed journals will be accepted. After the authenticity of the contributions
242 have been established, the data will be merged into the master dataset.

243 To facilitate these additions to the database, a page on the site is dedicated to importing
244 data (<http://emirockmechanicsdatabase.mines.edu/import.php>). The contributor must enter source
245 information, such as journal, article title, authors, date, and other publication information. Next,
246 the contributor is presented with a table into which they may enter rock specimen information as

247 well as any applicable rock mechanics data. The contributor may then submit the data, and once it
248 has been processed it will be added to the main rock mechanics database.

249

250 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

251 The EMI rock mechanics database described in this paper is a model that can be followed
252 to facilitate the organization, portrayal, and analysis of a large collection of rock mechanics data.
253 A modern database provides flexibility and organizational power that cannot be matched by other
254 tools. The database provides a simple scheme for organizing data in a modular and extensible
255 fashion. In addition, by using popular web technologies such as JavaScript, PHP and HTML/CSS,
256 it is straightforward to build a web-based interface that displays and analyzes data based on simple
257 filtering criteria. The true power of a rock mechanics database lies in the application-specific
258 customizability. While this implementation was oriented towards the statistical analysis of
259 correlations in different rock characteristics, numerous approaches are possible. Also, since the
260 database is well organized and simple to query, multiple frontend implementations with separate
261 approaches that utilize the same database can co-exist. A well-organized database is ultimately a
262 more sustainable and powerful approach to accessing rock mechanics data, contributing greatly to
263 the improvement of the cost-effectiveness of engineering processes and the safety of geotechnical
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272 **6. REFERENCES**

273 Benson DA, Cavanaugh M, Clark K, Karsch-Mizrachi I, Lipman DJ, Ostell J, Sayers EW (2013)
274 GenBank. Nucleic Acids Research 41:D36-D42
275 Ghassemi A (2012) A review of some rock mechanics issues in geothermal reservoir development.
276 Geotech Geol Eng 30:647-664

277 Goetze C, Evans B (1979) Stress and temperature in the bending lithosphere as constrained by
278 experimental rock mechanics. *Geophys J Int* 59:463-478

279 Jing L (2003) A review of techniques, advances and outstanding issues in numerical modelling for
280 rock mechanics and rock engineering. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 40:283-353

281 Kim E, Changani H (2016) Effect of water saturation and loading rate on the mechanical properties
282 of Red and Buff Sandstones. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 88:23–28

283 Kim E, Rostami J, Swope C (2009) Measurement of conical bit rotation. Paper presented at the
284 43rd U.S. Rock Mechanics Symposium & 4th U.S.-Canada Rock Mechanics Symposium,
285 Asheville, North Carolina, June 28 - July 1

286 Kim E, Rostami J, Swope C (2010) Full scale linear cutting test to study rotation of conical bit.
287 Paper presented at the 44th U.S. Rock Mechanics Symposium and 5th U.S.-Canada Rock
288 Mechanics Symposium, Salt Lake City, Utah, June 27-30

289 Kim E, Rostami J, Swope C (2012a) Full scale linear cutting experiment to examine conical bit
290 rotation. *J Min Sci* 48:882-895

291 Kim E, Rostami J, Swope C, Colvin S (2012b) Study of conical bit rotation using full-scale rotary
292 cutting experiments. *J Min Sci* 48:717-731

293 Liolios P, Exadaktylos G (2011) A relational rock mechanics database scheme with a hierarchical
294 structure. *Computers & Geosciences* 37:1192-1204

295 Perras M, Diederichs M (2014) A review of the tensile strength of rock: concepts and testing.
296 *Geotech Geol Eng* 32:525-546

297 Peters SE, Zhang C, Livny M, Ré C (2014) A machine reading system for assembling synthetic
298 paleontological databases. *PLOS ONE* 9:e113523

299 Schumacher FP, Kim E (2013) Modeling the pipe umbrella roof support system in a western US
300 underground coal mine. *Int J Rock Mech Min Sci* 60:114-124

301 Schumacher FP, Kim E (2014) Evaluation of directional drilling implication of double layered
302 pipe umbrella system for the coal mine roof support with composite material and beam
303 element methods using FLAC3D. *J Min Sci* 50:336-349

304 Sieter J, Smith M, Kim E, Cox S (2015) Dust and noise hazard exposure: Comparison of PDC
305 vs.WC roof bolt bits in laboratory. *Mining Engineering* 67:28–33

306

307 **Figure Legends**

308

309 **Figure 1.** AJAX (Asynchronous JavaScript and XML) architecture diagram.

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311

312 **Figure 2.** Schema design of EMI rock mechanics website.

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314

315 **Figure 3.** Data request form of EMI rock mechanics database. First selection of rock type and
316 characteristic (sedimentary sandstone selected) (A), second selection of rock type and
317 characteristic (unselected in the figure) (B), density and UCS selected as the property pair for the
318 plot (C), and results filtered by non-structural failure with all bedding (D).

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320

321 **Figure 4.** The EMI database plot between sandstone density and UCS (A), regression data (B),
322 and statistics results (C).

323

324

325 **Figure 5.** The EMI database plot of metamorphic gneiss and igneous granite with the correlation
326 between BTS and UCS.

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329 **Figure 6.** Data uploading function on the EMI rock mechanics database website by peer
330 researchers.

331

Figure 1. AJAX architecture diagram

Figure 4. The correlation between Sample Rock Mechanics Database Plot.

Figure 2. Schema design of EMI rock mechanics website.

Figure 5. The correlation between Sample Rock Mechanics Database Plot.

Figure 3. Data request form of EMI rock mechanics database. (A) First selection of rock type and characteristic (sedimentary sandstone selected), (B) second selection of rock type and characteristic (granite selected), (C) density and UCS selected as the property pair for the plot, and (D) results filtered by non-structural failures with all loading.

Figure 4. Data uploading function in the EMI rock mechanics database by peer researchers.